

FAIR for Machine Learning Model

Principles and Assessment Metrics

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Description	FAIR4ML Model defines a set of principles and their corresponding assessment – metrics and tests – for the evaluation of the FAIR principles for ML models.
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Versioning history

Version	Date	Description
1.0	September 17, 2024	The first release of the specification, consisting of 21 principles and the 27 assessment metrics.
1.0.1	October 8, 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - URL link to FAIRShake project - Scores for the manual assessment metrics - Double check the ML schema from RDA's FAIR4ML IG - Add the third test to ML-R3-01M;
1.0.2	January 21, 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changed "Disclaimer" to "Acknowledgement"
1.1	February 25, 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The assessment for the practical test for ML-A2-01M changed to "Manual/Automatic". - The assessment for the practical tests for ML-R3-02S changed to "Manual/Automatic". - The assessment for the practical tests for ML-R3-01M changed to "Manual/Automatic". - Add a note about scoring the practical tests (in Section D). - Remove the practical test number 3 from ML-R1.7-01M and include it instead as a practical test for ML-R1.7-02M.

	November 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Remove principle A2 (removed in the latest DOAM version (v0.8))- Typos
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A. Introduction

The rise of data science and AI-related research artifacts such as Machine Learning (ML) models requires increased visibility and reuse within and across research communities. To this end, we explored the adoption of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), specifying how such an adoption could look like (a FAIR model) in terms of applicable *principles* and a set of corresponding *metrics* and *tests* to enable its assessment.

The **FAIR4ML Model** specification consists of (i) a specification of FAIR principles for ML models, and (ii) a set of evaluation metrics and tests to enable the assessment of those principles.

FAIR4ML Model adopts many of the principles from FAIR Principles for Research Software Version 1.0 (FAIR4RS) (Chue Hong et al., 2022) and to different extents – from complete adoption (no changes) to introduction of new ones dedicated to ML models. In total, there are **20** principles for this model: we adopted the majority (14 principles) from FAIR4RS, 1 from Wilkinson et al. (2016), and introduced five new ones dedicated to ML models. Section B, “FAIR4ML Model Principles”, provides the complete set of principles.

The **FAIR4ML Model assessment framework** is based on RDA’s FAIR Data Maturity Model (DMM) (FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, 2020) and FAIRsFAIR’s Data Object Assessment Metrics (DOAM) (Devaraju et al., 2022), consisting of **26** metrics and **54** tests. We mainly base the framework on existing works - DOAM (16 metrics) and the DMM (2 metrics), with changes – adoption and inclusion of new metrics, wherever necessary, including newly-introduced ones (8 metrics). Section C, “FAIR4ML Model Metrics”, provides the complete set of metrics and practical tests for our proposal.

Table 1 list the FAIR principles, metrics and corresponding tests according to the framework they have been adopted from, as well as the newly introduced ones in the FAIR4ML Model. We can note the overlap of the different artifact types – datasets, research software, and ML models – both in terms of FAIR principles, and assessment metrics, which is to be expected due to some of their features. For example, persistent identification, or rich (metadata) description, to name but a few, apply in the same way for all these artifact types.

	Principles			Metrics			
	FAIR4RS	Wilkinson et al.	New	DOAM	DMM	New	Tests
Findable	5			5		1	13
Accessible	2			3	1		6
Interoperable	2	1		3			6
Reusable	3		7	5	1	7	29
Total		20			26		54

Table 1. **FAIR4ML Model**: Principles, metrics, and tests

Excluding the cases of small rewrites or adoptions¹, there are notable differences between FAIR4ML Model and FAIR4RS. Namely, as far as the assessment metrics go, the new metrics relate to assessing principles from the Reusable FAIR category, which, in a way, shows the importance of a dedicated FAIR model for ML models.

¹ This would include using “ML model” instead of “Software” or “Dataset”, for example.

B. FAIR4ML Model Principles

As mentioned in the introductory part, **FAIR4ML Model** adopts many of the principles from FAIR4RS. However, the ML model features require specific aspects, across all the FAIR categories, that needed to be addressed. This included introducing new principles to cover ML model specificities, as well as adopting principles from the original FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

FAIR4ML Models consists of **20** principles (Table 2), with change types including the following:

- **Adapted** These changes are minimal and usually include using “ML model” instead of “software” or “software component” as terms in a principle. This is the most frequent change in this work (applied for **thirteen** principles across the four FAIR categories). Finally, in one case, we denote a principle as I3 in FAIR4ML Model, although it was denoted as I2 in FAIR4RS.
- **Rewritten** In **one** case, we had to rewrite a principle from the source model to reflect the requirements of ML models. This was the case when discussing the use of an ML model vs that of a software (I1 principle in FAIR4ML Model).
- **Remains the same** Some of the principles are quite generic, thus rendering them applicable across different resource types. This type of change occurs in **two** cases related to the Accessible principles, which are more general, such as the role of open protocols and the metadata.
- **N/A** This type of change includes **two** cases: (i) a principle does not apply to ML models, and (ii) a principle is too detailed, often requiring more (manual) effort to assess. We had one occurrence for each case - the F1.1 principle from FAIR4RS did not apply to ML models, whereas we omitted the A1.1 from the model altogether. For the latter, while important in providing as high access as possible to a resource, it is not often the case that publication platforms (repositories, research data infrastructures, etc.) employ proprietary communication protocols.
- **New**: These principles only refer to ML models and are applied in **five** cases.

Principle	FAIR4ML Models
F	ML model and its associated metadata is easy for both humans and machines to find.
<i>F1</i>	ML model is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
<i>F1.1</i>	Different versions of ML model are assigned distinct identifiers.
<i>F2</i>	ML model is described with rich metadata.
<i>F3</i>	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the ML model they describe.
<i>F4</i>	Metadata are FAIR, searchable and indexable.
A	ML model and its metadata are retrievable via standardized protocols.
<i>A1</i>	ML model is retrievable by its identifier using a standardized communications protocol.
<i>A1.1</i>	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
I	An ML model offers its serialized knowledge to support decisions on data.
<i>I1</i>	ML model uses a knowledge representation in a way that meets domain-relevant community standards.
<i>I2</i>	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles ²
<i>I3</i>	ML model includes qualified references to other objects.
R	ML model is both usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other ML models).
<i>R1</i>	ML model is described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.

² Adopted from the FAIR principles from Wilkinson et al. (2016).

<i>R1.1</i>	ML model is given a clear and accessible license.
<i>R1.2</i>	ML model is associated with detailed provenance.
<i>R1.3</i>	ML model type is described with relevant attributes.
<i>R1.4</i>	ML model dataset is described with relevant attributes.
<i>R1.5</i>	ML model learning algorithm implementation (code) is described with relevant attributes.
<i>R1.6</i>	ML model hyper-parameters are described with relevant attributes.
<i>R1.7</i>	ML model training and evaluation processes are described with relevant attributes.
<i>R2</i>	ML model includes qualified references to other ML models.
<i>R3</i>	ML model meets domain-relevant community standards.

Table 2. FAIR4ML Models principles

The new principles we included in FAIR4ML Model are the result of common requirements for ML models, such as the training process, dataset provenance, model training parameters, etc. That is why we included principles to cover additional aspects of an ML model, such as their type, dataset, learning algorithm, hyper-parameters, and training and evaluation. For the principles we adopt from FAIR4RS we invite the reader to consult the corresponding references.

C. FAIR4ML Model Metrics

FAIR4ML Model assessment framework consists of **26** metrics. We follow the naming convention from FAIRsFAIR’s DOAM framework: each name starts with “ML” as a short reference to “ML models”, followed by the FAIR principle and a local identifier (incremented for every metric identified). Since metrics can be applied to both metadata and ML models, there is a final part in the metric name to indicate this - “S” for ML model and “M” for metadata. Table 3 provides the complete list of metrics, including information on their source – if they were adopted from existing frameworks, or if they were newly-introduced.

Some frameworks assign different scores or weights to their metrics. For all the metrics we adopt from DOAM and DMM, we also adopt the same description and scoring (say that by F-UJI³ from DOAM). For the description of the metrics, we keep a short version to avoid textual clutter and repetition but also provide a brief description about the assessment aim of every metric. Table 5 in Appendix B provides all the metrics, including the test cases for each. Finally, you can see the representation of these metrics in the FAIRShake project⁴ that we use for the evaluation.

FAIR Principle	Identifier	Metric name	DMM / DOAM / NEW
Findable ML model and its associated metadata is easy for both humans and machines to find.			
F1	ML-F1-01S	ML model is assigned a globally unique identifier.	DOAM FsF-F1-01D
F1	ML-F1-02S	ML model is assigned a persistent identifier.	DOAM FsF-F1-02D
F1.1	ML-F1.1-01S	Different versions of ML model are assigned different identifiers.	New
F2	ML-F2-01M	Metadata includes descriptive core elements to support data findability.	DOAM FsF-F2-01M
F3	ML-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier of the ML model it describes.	DOAM

³ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

⁴ <https://fairshake.cloud/project/218/>

			FsF-F3-01M
F4	ML-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	DOAM FsF-F4-01M
Accessible ML model and its metadata are retrievable via standardized protocols.			
A1	ML-A1-01M	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the ML model.	DOAM FsF-A1-01M
A1	ML-A1-02M	Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.	DOAM FsF-A1-02M
A1	ML-A1-03S	ML model is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.	DOAM FsF-A1-03D
A1.1	ML-A1.1-01S	ML model is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorization.	DMM RDA-A1.2-01D
Interoperable An ML model offers its serialized knowledge to support decisions on data.			
I1	ML-I1-01M	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	DOAM FsF-I1-01M
I2	ML-I2-01M	Metadata uses semantic resources.	DOAM FsF-I2-01M
I3	ML-I3-01M	Metadata includes links between the ML model and its related entities.	DOAM FsF-I3-01M
Reusable ML model is both usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other ML models).			
R1	ML-R1-01M	Metadata specifies the content of the ML model.	DOAM FsF-R1-01MD
R1.1	ML-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes license information under which ML model can be reused.	DOAM FsF-R1.1-01M
R1.2	ML-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information about ML model creation or generation.	DOAM FsF-R1.2-01M
R1.3	ML-R1.3-01M	Metadata includes information about ML model type.	New
R1.4	ML-R1.4-01M	Metadata includes information about the dataset used for ML model training, testing and validation.	New
R1.4	ML-R1.4-02M	Metadata includes information about ML model dataset collection process.	New
R1.5	ML-R1.5-01M	Metadata includes information about ML model source code.	New
R1.6	ML-R1.6-01M	Metadata describes ML model hyper-parameters.	New
R1.7	ML-R1.7-01M	Metadata describes ML model training process.	New
R1.7	ML-R1.7-02M	Metadata describes ML model evaluation.	New
R2	ML-R2-01M	Metadata contains references to other ML models.	DMM RDA-I3-04M ⁵
R3	ML-R3-01M	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the ML model.	DOAM FsF-R1.3-01M
R3	ML-R3-02S	ML model is available in a file format recommended by the ML community.	DOAM FsF-R1.3-02D

Table 3. FAIR4ML Model assessment framework

⁵ Note: The FAIR4RS framework puts this principle as R2, but we map it to metric I3 from DMM.

When specifying assessment metrics, there are many assumptions to consider. Such assumptions are usually based on the practices of the target communities. On this note, we next comment on few of the assessment metrics of the FAIR4ML Model framework, which we believe will additionally help understand its assessment. Grouped on the individual FAIR principles for ease of reference, this includes:

Findable

ML-F2-01M: Metadata includes descriptive core elements to support data findability.

The DOAM framework specifies the “descriptive core elements” it targets in the metadata for this metric. However, anyone applying this FAIR assessment framework can specify the list of such elements – either by considering additional elements based on their community practices or omitting existing ones that do not apply to their case.

Accessible

ML-A1-02M and ML-A1-03S: Metadata and ML model are accessible through a standardized communication protocol.

To keep the list of metrics that enable a fully automatic assessment, we considered keeping as few manual assessments as possible. This was the case regarding these two metrics. However, combining these metrics in one would not be suitable when assessing a case that fulfills one, but not the other aspect of the principle. Thus, we kept them both for a more complete FAIR assessment.

Interoperable

ML-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the ML model and its related entities.

The DOAM framework lists a few candidates for this metric about the entities that a resource could link to. In our case, such references can be anything that is related to the ML model. This includes aspects such as ML model’s prior version, related datasets, resources (publications, repositories, platforms, etc.), and so on. This principle covers all non-ML model references.

Reusable

ML-R1-01M: Metadata specifies the content of the ML model.

Examples from DOAM framework for this metric include the resource type (e.g., data or a collection of data), variable(s) measured or observed, method, data format and size. As with the previous cases, ML community practices that specify an ML model accurately is desirable for this metric.

ML-R1.2-01M: Metadata includes provenance information about ML model creation or generation.

Examples from the DOAM framework include sources of data, data creation or collection date, contributors involved in data creation and their roles, data publication, modification and versioning information. The ML community could provide its own elements to consider when assessing this metric.

As far as the disciplinary metrics introduced are concerned – metrics from *ML-R1.3-01M* to *ML-R1.7-02M*, we do not suggest any specific level of details or practice. Instead, we leave it to the community to find a set of metadata that reflect the practices (how they document ML model evaluation or hyperparameters, for example) they adhere to that do not burden the ML model documentation and publication process. This, in turn, enables a better application of FAIR principles and their corresponding assessment by the ML communities.

ML-R2-01M: Metadata contains references to other related ML models.

This metric has similarities to *ML-I3-01M*. While *ML-I3-01M* refers to general references, that is, all references that are related to the ML model, **ML-R2-01M** specifically refers to ML models used to extend from/develop an ML model. This includes information about the way it is connected to other ML models. Being a qualified reference, the connection or relationship needs to be specified, such as *ML model X is based on/extends ML model Y*.

ML-R3-01M: Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target ML community.

Adopting community standards has been emphasized for several principles already, and this is the requirement of this metric. Some communities have established metadata standards and the use of metadata standards supported by the community is usually promoted and established by repositories of the ML domain. The MEX lightweight metadata standard (Esteves et al., 2015) or the Machine Learning DCAT Application Profile (MLDCAT-AP) are but two such examples.

ML-R3-02S: ML model is available in a file format recommended by the ML community.

The ML model adheres to the standards of the ML community, thus it uses a widely used file format for knowledge representation⁶. While the file format can seem like a minimal aspect of an ML model, we consider it as just an initial step to assess the extent to which an ML model conforms to community standards. This, however, can be extended to accommodate any new/emerging recommendations (beyond the file format).

It is important to treat these aspects as enabling the ML community further specify the assessment metrics according to their practices, resulting with applicable metrics for FAIR assessment of their ML model collections. Thus, we expect that communities that deal with ML models, across domains, to conduct such customizations and evolve the metrics for ML models in this specification.

D. Outlook

During the process of specifying a FAIR model and its assessment, we went through several iterations. Initially we started with a larger set of principles and corresponding metrics, which we then reconsidered to keep the essential and practical ones for the final version.

Ideally, the FAIR assessment for ML models should be fully automatic, especially considering the pace with which such artifacts are being created and exchanged. However, this is not always possible, and metrics that require manual assessment are part of FAIR specifications. Moreover, when it comes to the FAIR assessment, not all metrics have the same impact toward the final score, and many assessment frameworks indicate this. In the case of the DMM framework, for example, there are the *essential*, *important* and *useful* categories of importance for its metrics, whereas DOAM adopts different *scores* for the tests. In the context of FAIR4ML Model, when considering the metrics for the principles from R1.3 to R1.7, for example, based on the community feedback we gathered during our iterations, those associated to R1.6 and R1.7 are of a relatively lower importance than the rest.

On the topic of scope, FAIR models usually come with a certain flexibility: if a community deems additional principles and/or metrics necessary, they can extend a FAIR specification accordingly. On another hand, if a community finds a few of the principles and/or metrics with a lower priority and aims towards a fully automatic assessment, for example, they might reduce the FAIR specification accordingly. Moreover, scoring the practical tests of the metrics is also community dependent, and another consideration when adopting the FAIR principles. In the same vein as considering or omitting metrics, a community can specify the scoring of the practical tests for every metric based on their weight or importance to the overall FAIR assessment for ML models.

Finally, for some of the assessment metrics it becomes important to reflect community-specific practices. While adhering to the suggestions from the corresponding assessment frameworks we adopt is a first step, considering specific requirements remains an important part of the ML model FAIR assessment. This includes not only metrics specific to ML models, but also other standards and practices that enable a more

⁶ Consider the following list as such an example: <https://github.com/trailofbits/ml-file-formats>.

complete description and enable an easier reuse of ML models. We mention such relevant standards and practices in several cases – both for FAIR principles and metrics – to point out their value and application to the FAIR adoption and assessment for the communities working with ML model artifacts.

In concluding this specification, we provide a key quick information about the **FAIR4ML Model**:

FAIR4ML Model: A profile card	
Artifact	ML model
FAIR principles	Custom, based on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wilkinson et al. (2016), and - FAIR4RS Principles v1.0.
	- 20 principles
FAIR assessment	Custom, based on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.5), and - RDA's FAIR Data Maturity Model
	- 26 assessment metrics
	- 54 practical tests
Assessment method	Hybrid, with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automatic: For 16 metrics - Manual: For 10 metrics
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A configurable survey tool (FAIRShake), with corresponding rubrics, and - An automatic assessment tool (F-UJI)

Table 4. A review: Key information of FAIR4ML Model

E. References

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F. Appendix

A. FAIR Principles: FAIR4RS and FAIR4ML Model Comparison

Since we primarily extend **FAIR4RS** (Chue Hong et al., 2022), we first list its principles, followed by those of the **FAIR4ML Model**. To indicate the level to which we adopt or extend these principles, including introducing new ones, we also provide brief information about it in the last column of the table.

	FAIR for Research Software	FAIR for ML Model	Change type
<i>F</i>	Software, and its associated metadata, is easy for both humans and machines to find.	ML model and its associated metadata is easy for both humans and machines to find.	
<i>F1</i>	Software is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.	ML model is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.	Adapted
<i>F1.1</i>	Components of the software representing levels of granularity are assigned distinct identifiers.	-	N/A
<i>F1.2</i>	Different versions of the software are assigned distinct identifiers.	Different versions of the ML models are assigned distinct identifiers. ⁷	Adapted
<i>F2</i>	Software is described with rich metadata.	ML model is described with rich metadata.	Adapted
<i>F3</i>	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the software they describe.	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the ML model they describe.	Adapted
<i>F4</i>	Metadata are FAIR, searchable and indexable.	Metadata are FAIR, searchable and indexable.	Remains the same
<i>A</i>	Software, and its metadata, is retrievable via standardized protocols.	ML model and its metadata are retrievable via standardized protocols.	
<i>A1</i>	Software is retrievable by its identifier using a standardized communications protocol.	ML model is retrievable by its identifier using a standardized communications protocol.	Adapted
<i>A1.1</i>	The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.	⁸	N/A
<i>A1.2</i>	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary. ⁹	Remains the same
<i>A2</i>	Metadata are accessible, even when the software is no longer available.	Not included due to its assessment challenge!	N/A
<i>I</i>	Software interoperates with other software by exchanging data and/or metadata, and/or through interaction via application programming interfaces (APIs), described through standards.	An ML model offers its serialized knowledge to support decisions on data.	

⁷ This is the F1.1 principle in **FAIR4ML Model**, but we keep it in this row to show the difference to FAIR4RS.

⁸ Even though it can apply to ML models, we omit it to enable a more automatic FAIR assessment.

⁹ This is the A1.1 principle in **FAIR4ML Model**, but we keep it in this row to show the difference to FAIR4RS.

I1	Software reads, writes and exchanges data in a way that meets domain-relevant community standards.	ML model uses a knowledge representation in a way that meets domain-relevant community standards.	Rewritten
I2	Software includes qualified references to other objects. ¹⁰	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles. ¹¹	Adapted
I3	-	ML model includes qualified references to other objects.	Adapted
R	Software is both usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other software).	ML model is both usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other ML models).	
R1	Software is described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.	ML model is described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.	Adapted
R1.1	Software is given a clear and accessible license.	ML model is given a clear and accessible license.	Adapted
R1.2	Software is associated with detailed provenance.	ML model is associated with detailed provenance.	Adapted
R1.3	-	ML model type is described with relevant attributes.	New
R1.4	-	ML model dataset is described with relevant attributes.	New
R1.5	-	ML model learning algorithm implementation (code) is described with relevant attributes.	New
R1.6	-	ML model hyper-parameters are described with relevant attributes.	New
R1.7	-	ML model training and evaluation processes are described with relevant attributes.	New
R2	Software includes qualified references to other software.	ML model includes qualified references to other ML models.	Adapted
R3	Software meets domain-relevant community standards.	ML model meets domain-relevant community standards.	Adapted

Table 4. FAIR4ML principles: A comparison between FAIR4RS and FAIR4ML Models

B. FAIR assessment: Metrics and tests

The DOAM framework (Devaraju et al., 2022) serves as our primary source for the FAIR assessment FAIR4ML Model. Thus, for every FAIR principle applicable to ML models, we list the corresponding metric(s), test(s), as well as a rationale for such a test. Additionally, as part of the rationale, we provide the assessment method (manual vs automatic) for every metric. Finally, we provide this information as part of the online publication of the metrics at our FAIRShake project¹², including objects – ML models – that we FAIR assess.

FAIR4ML Model metrics	Tests	Rationale
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¹⁰ We treat this aspect as more of an I3 principle and represent it accordingly in our model.

¹¹ This principle is adapted from the original FAIR principles from Wilkinson et al. (2016).

¹² <https://fairshake.cloud/rubric/146/>

F1	<p>ML-F1-01S ML model is assigned a globally unique identifier. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/611/</p>	<p>1) Identifier is not resolvable, but follows a UUID or HASH type syntax.</p> <p>2) Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax (URL, IRL).</p>	<p>An ML model is assigned a global unique identifier such that it can be referenced unambiguously by humans or machines.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
F1	<p>ML-F1-02S ML model is assigned a persistent identifier. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/612/</p>	<p>1) Identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax.</p> <p>2) Persistent identifier is resolvable (landing page can be reached).</p>	<p>An ML model is assigned a persistent identifier such that it can be resolved (point) to a landing page with metadata containing further information on the resource.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
F1.1	<p>ML-F1.1-01S Different versions of ML model are assigned different identifiers. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/613/</p>	<p>1) Identifiers for different versions follow a defined persistent identifier syntax.</p> <p>2) Persistent identifiers are resolvable (landing page can be reached).</p>	<p>An ML model can have different versions. It takes changing one element of an ML project, such as hyperparameters or the source code (to improve the training efficacy, for example), to result with a different ML model (version). In this case, each such version should be assigned a unique identifier to enable a researcher to clearly identify a specific version of an ML model.</p> <p>Assessment: Manual</p>
F2	<p>ML-F2-01M Metadata includes descriptive core elements to support data findability. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/614/</p>	<p>1) Some metadata has been made available via common web methods (embedded, typed links, content negotiation).</p> <p>2) Core data citation metadata is available.</p> <p>3) Core descriptive metadata is available.</p>	<p>Metadata has descriptive information about an ML model. This metric focuses on domain-independent, core (and minimum) metadata.¹³</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
F3	<p>ML-F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier of the ML model it describes. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/615/</p>	<p>1) Metadata contains ML model content related information (file name, size, type).</p> <p>2) Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable ML model content.</p>	<p>The metadata should explicitly specify the identifier of the ML model (content) such that users can discover and access it through the metadata.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
F4	<p>ML-F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/616/</p>	<p>1) Metadata is registered in major research data registries (DataCite).</p> <p>2) Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (JSON-LD, Dublin Core, RDFa).</p>	<p>Metadata can be made available in different ways via different standards, protocols, embedded as structured data in Web pages, etc. This metric only refers to its representation aspect, ensuring that the ways through which the metadata is exposed or provided</p>

¹³ We adopt the corresponding elements defined by Devaraju et al. (2022)

			is based on a standard and machine-readable format.
A1	<p>ML-A1-01M Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the ML model. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/617/</p>	<p>1) Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in the metadata.</p> <p>2) ML model access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms.</p> <p>3) ML model access information is machine readable.</p>	<p>Assessment: Automatic</p> <p>This metric determines if the metadata includes the level of access to the ML model data, such as public, embargoed, restricted, or metadata-only access, and its access conditions.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
A1	<p>ML-A1-02M Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/618/</p>	<p>1) Landing page link is based on standardized web communication protocols.</p>	<p>Given an identifier of a dataset, the metadata of the dataset should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
A1	<p>ML-A1-03S ML model is accessible through a standardized communication protocol. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/619/</p>	<p>1) Metadata includes a resolvable link to ML model based on a standardized web communication protocol.</p>	<p>Given an identifier of a dataset, the dataset should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
A1.1	<p>ML-A1.1-01S ML model is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorization. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/620/</p>	<p>1) The indicator can be evaluated by assessing whether an authentication and authorisation process is present in the protocol.</p>	<p>The indicator requires that if the ML model or local environment indicates a degree of additional protection, then the access protocol must support authentication and authorisation of people and/or machines.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
I1	<p>ML-I1-01M Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/622/</p>	<p>1) Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code.</p> <p>2) Parsable, graph data (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or SPARQL endpoint.</p>	<p>Expressing the metadata of a data object using a formal knowledge representation will enable machines to process it in a meaningful way and enable more data exchange possibilities.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>
I2	<p>ML-I2-01M Metadata uses semantic resources. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/623/</p>	<p>1) Vocabulary namespace URIs can be identified in metadata.</p> <p>2) Namespaces of known semantic resources can be identified in metadata.</p>	<p>A metadata document or selected parts of the document may incorporate additional terms from semantic resources that unambiguously describe the contents so they can be processed automatically by machines.</p>

Assessment: Automatic

R3

ML-I3-01M Metadata includes links between the ML model and its related entities.

<https://fairshake.cloud/metric/624/>

- 1) Related resources are explicitly mentioned in metadata.
- 2) Related resources are indicated by machine readable links or identifiers.

Linking an ML model to its related entities (used libraries, platforms, parameters, datasets, configuration file for execution, etc.) will increase its potential for reuse. The linking information should be captured as part of the metadata. Is possible, persistent identifiers should be used for the corresponding related entities, such as ORCID for contributors, DOI for publications, and ROR for institutions, etc.

Assessment: Automatic

R1

ML-R1-01M Metadata specifies the content of the ML model.

<https://fairshake.cloud/metric/625/>

- 1) Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata (resource type, links).
- 2) Verifiable data descriptors (file info (size, type), measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata.
- 3) Data content matches measured variables or file type and size specified in metadata.

This metric evaluates if the content of the dataset is specified in the metadata, and it should be an accurate reflection of the actual data deposited.

Assessment: Automatic

R1.1

ML-R1.1-01M Metadata includes license information under which ML model can be reused.

<https://fairshake.cloud/metric/626/>

- 1) License information is given in an appropriate metadata element.
- 2) Recognized license is valid, actionable and registered at a license registry (e.g., SPDX).

This metric evaluates if data is associated with a license because otherwise users cannot reuse it in a clear legal context.

Assessment: Automatic

R1.2

ML-R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information about ML model creation or generation.

<https://fairshake.cloud/metric/627/>

- 1) Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information and can be mapped to PROV.
- 2) Metadata contains provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O).

Data provenance represents a ML model's history, including the people, entities, and processes involved in its creation, management and longer-term curation.

Assessment: Automatic

R1.3

ML-R1.3-01M Metadata includes information about ML model type.

<https://fairshake.cloud/metric/628/>

- 1) The model type is described.
- 2) The complexity of the learning algorithm is explained.
- 3) The limitations of the algorithm are mentioned.

Information about the ML model type is important towards the better understanding and easier reuse of an ML model. This is a disciplinary requirement.

Assessment: Manual

R1.4

ML-R1.4-01M Metadata includes information about the dataset used for ML model training, testing and validation.

- 1) The dataset is mentioned and its properties are explained.

Information about the dataset used for training, validation and testing of an ML model is important towards the better

	https://fairshake.cloud/metric/629/	2) The breakdown of the data for the individual phases (training, testing, and validation) is explained.	understanding and easier reuse of an ML model. This is a disciplinary requirement.
R1.4	ML-R1.4-02M Metadata includes information about ML model dataset collection process. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/630/	1) The origin of the data is described. 2) A link for downloading or obtaining the dataset is described.	Assessment: Manual This information could enable an easier reuse of the dataset used for the ML model (training, validation, and testing). As such, details around its creating, including any transformations, should be listed. This is a disciplinary requirement.
R1.5	ML-R1.5-01M Metadata includes information about ML model source code. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/631/	1) The code to download is included with the model. 2) There is a link to a software repository to download the code from.	Assessment: Manual Essential properties of ML model source code, such as dependencies, libraries, code repository, etc., are important to enable code reuse. A link to the appropriate software repository with all information is desirable. This is a disciplinary requirement.
R1.6	ML-R1.6-01M Metadata describes ML model hyperparameters. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/632/	1) The hyperparameters of the model are named. 2) A guide to choosing the right hyperparameters is described.	Assessment: Manual Hyperparameters control the learning process of an ML model, thus they are important in to form/understand the context of an ML model and, ultimately, of its reusability. This is a disciplinary requirement.
R1.7	ML-R1.7-01M Metadata describes ML model training process. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/633/	1) The learning process is explained. 2) The hardware on which the learning process runs is named.	Assessment: Manual The training process of the ML model should also be described in the metadata. Several aspects of training should be taken into account, such as the preprocessing, actual training, the test process for configuring the model, and so on. The infrastructure of the training environment should also be described. This is a disciplinary requirement.
R1.7	ML-R1.7-02M Metadata describes ML model evaluation. https://fairshake.cloud/metric/634/	1) The result of the learning process is explained and described.	Assessment: Manual ML model evaluation should be described with all notable indicators, such as confusion matrix, F1 score, Area Under the ROC Curve, etc. The indicators should demonstrate and describe the quality and performance of

			the model. This is a disciplinary requirement.
R2	<p>ML-R2-01M Metadata contains references to other ML models.</p> <p>https://fairshake.cloud/metric/635/</p>	<p>1) Relations to ML models are provided with a URL for further information.</p>	<p>Assessment: Manual</p> <p>Related ML models should be referred to as a qualitative reference. Here too, the relation object should be described by a relation type (such as DataCite Metadata Schema); Persistent identifiers should preferably be used (DOI for software), and if possible, GUIDs as well.</p>
R3	<p>ML-R3-01M Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the ML model.</p> <p>https://fairshake.cloud/metric/636/</p>	<p>1) Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the ML model.</p> <p>2) Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata or metadata services outputs.</p> <p>3) Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, fairsharing) standard is listed in the re3data record or detected by namespace.</p>	<p>Assessment: Manual</p> <p>In addition to making core and other relevant metadata available to support data discovery, this should be made following community-endorsed metadata standards.</p> <p>The use of community-supported metadata standards is usually encouraged and established by ML domain repositories. Such metadata standards should be published in corresponding registries, such as the re3data, for example.</p>
R3	<p>ML-R3-02S ML model is available in a file format recommended by the ML community.</p> <p>https://fairshake.cloud/metric/637/</p>	<p>1) The format of the data file is an open format.</p> <p>2) The format of the data file is a long-term format.</p> <p>3) The format of the data file is a scientific format.</p>	<p>Assessment: Manual/Automatic</p> <p>Data should be made available in a file format that is backed by the research community to enable data sharing and reuse.</p> <p>Assessment: Automatic</p>

Table 5. FAIR4ML Model assessment metrics and tests